

PERSPECTIVES ON INTEGRATED APPROACH TO FOOD SAFETY

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ABSTRACT

Food is universal to man as well as animals which also provide a bulk of the food needed by man. The current population of the world stands at about 7 billion. With this increasing population is also the increasing need to provide not just food but also healthy food for the consumption of man. In this paper we examine the integrated approach to food safety in order to meet the need for healthy food by man and in a healthy manner to all the occupants of the planet whether plants or animals. This is even more important considering new trends in outbreaks of food-borne diseases around the world such as the recent outbreak caused by *Escherichia coli* 0104:H4 in Europe and the United States which is said to be the worst outbreak in history.

KEYWORDS: Integrated, food, safety, *E.coli*, outbreak, population

INTRODUCTION

The integrated approach to food safety aims to assure a high level of food safety, animal health, animal welfare and plant health through coherent farm-to-table measures and adequate monitoring and surveillance, while ensuring the effective functioning of the market thereby ensuring maximum human health benefits and productivity (Buncic, 2006).

This approach is the sum total of all measures necessary from “farm to fork” and “stable to table” to ensure that food consumed by man is wholesome and of the highest possible quality standard. Due to the interlinked nature of food production such a strategy will require the assessment and monitoring of the risks to consumer health beginning with raw materials at the earliest possible stage in the food chain (Brackett, 1999).

From this initial focus, farming practices and food marketing or processing activities are then a logical progression; it requires regulatory action to manage this risk; and it requires the development and operation of adaptable control systems to monitor and enforce the regulations designed to encompass these processes. Each element constitutes an equally important part of a complex web; thus changes or advancements in food processing might lead to updating of existing safeguards, whilst feedback from the frontline primary producers can help to earlier identify and manage both existing and emerging risks. Each part of this chain must gel seamlessly for the achievement of highest possible food safety standards for the public (AFCD, 2011; Duffy *et al.*, 2008).

The primary responsibility for food safety lies with those who produce, process, transport, store and market/trade the food such as the farmers, fishermen, slaughter house operators, food processors, wholesale and retail traders, the caterers, e.t.c. The onus lies on them to ensure that food that will be ultimately consumed by man satisfies the highest possible health standard (Reid *et al.*, 2002). The supervisory authorities lay down the required standards and monitor compliance with it. Then the consumer must ensure personal hygiene and that food storage and preparation is done according to standard practices. Importantly the consumer is the one who decides what to eat and how to eat it: wisdom is required here to ensure that certain foods that are not needed are not consumed. If consumers are not careful in this respect they could be “digging their own graves with their teeth” by consuming certain foods not needed by the body or higher doses than required for some food (Newell *et al.*, 2010).

In order to maximize food safety a holistic approach is imperative and hence it is important that care is exercised throughout the whole food production-processing-distribution chain. Previously, food control often concentrated on the examination of end products and on inspection of food processing operations. However, in recent decades there has been a growing awareness of the importance of an integrated, multidisciplinary approach considering the whole of the food chain (and in some cases beyond what is conventionally regarded as the food chain). One

result of this change in approach is a much greater awareness of the need for better control on the composition and safety of animal feed. In response to this the Codex Alimentarius Commission established an *ad hoc* Task Force on Animal Feed and in recent years the European Community has introduced much more legislation and control on animal feed. Another result of the paradigm shift is a realization of the need for much closer contact and more interaction between those responsible for food control and those responsible for preventing or reducing environmental pollution. Such pollution, for example with persistent chemicals such as mercury, Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) and dioxins, can lead to food safety problems. Coupled to this there is now a greater emphasis on source-directed preventive measures (Slorach, 2005).

Measures involved in integrated approach to food safety

Some of the measures involved in the integrated approach to food safety include the following:

(a) Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points (HACCP) approach:

Food producers, processors and traders should operate according to the principles of Good Agricultural/Hygienic/Manufacturing Practices. Food production, processing and other handling operations should be analyzed with a view to identifying hazards and assessing associated risks. This should lead to the identification of critical control points and the establishment of a system to monitor production at these points (i.e. the Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Point – “HACCP” approach). The introduction of HACCP-based in-house control may be difficult in small and medium-sized enterprises with limited basic knowledge, experience and resources and is probably best achieved by collaboration between the food industry, education and training organizations and the supervisory authorities. The Codex Alimentarius and its parent organizations namely; the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) and the World Health Organization (WHO) have produced useful guidelines and training and information materials on the application of HACCP in food control in order to maximize food safety (Smulders and Greer, 1998).

(b) Prevention is better than cure principle:

It is always better to ensure that the level of contaminants in food and food related products is reduced to the barest minimum by controlling the sources of contamination, processing to reduce the level of contaminants, and employing measures to separate contaminated food from food fit and wholesome for human consumption (Pires *et al.*, 2011).

(c) Pesticides and Veterinary Drugs:

In order to ensure effective and maximum benefits from antimicrobial therapy, such drugs should only be used by qualified personnel and the indiscriminate use of pesticides in crops meant for human consumption should be monitored and discouraged. Pesticides levels should be monitored in water and food and levels of residues should be made known to the public if acceptable levels are exceeded (Gálvez *et al.*, 2010).

(d) Mycotoxins: Aflatoxins, ochratoxin A, patulin and trichotecenes, e.t.c. are notorious contaminants of food and critical control and preventive measures along the food chain must be taken to ensure that such contamination is not allowed at any point. This will involve measures being taken at the Pre-harvest and Post-harvest stages (White *et al.*, 2002).

(e) Persistent Environmental Pollutants: certain chemical emissions such as dioxins, Polychlorinated Biphenyls (PCBs), mercury, cadmium, e.t.c. have been known to be major contaminants of food. Fish from water contaminated with these chemicals are potential sources of hazard to man and as such should not be consumed. The level of emissions from industries should be monitored to restrict its going above acceptable limits detrimental to human health or animal life. In some countries especially in Europe, the Codex Committee on Food Additives and Contaminants is developing a code of practice to reduce dioxin contamination of food. Likewise some countries have legislated bans on the use of some potentially dangerous compounds such as lead and some pesticides (Newell *et al.*, 2010).

(f) Reforming Meat Inspection: the old traditional method of meat inspection that cannot diagnose symptomless carriers of infection hence allowing it to be carried to consumers is gradually being replaced by more comprehensive methods that allow for diagnosis of potentially dangerous zoonoses. In order to revamp meat inspection The Codex Alimentarius Commission has decided to start new work in this field and the Codex

Committee on Meat and Poultry Hygiene at the international level (Newell *et al.*, 2010; Reid *et al.*, 2002). Local authorities should ensure implementation of standard hygiene practices during meat inspection.

(g)Emerging Risks: We live in a world with rapid developments in science and technology, but also of rapid changes in the risks posed by microbiological and chemical hazards. It is therefore important that agencies responsible for food safety have a “reconnaissance” or “intelligence” function with the task of detecting emerging risks. These risks could be due to emerging pathogens, for example pathogens resistant to a wide range of antibiotics, the use of new feed components, new industrial or domestic chemicals, new production, processing and handling methods or to changes in dietary habits (Newell *et al.*, 2010).

(h)Traceability of food products: In order to ensure that the source of food safety problems is identified easily and traced back in the food chain certain countries in the developed world have started this system whereby such food problems can be traced back and legislations are underway to make this a requirement in many countries around the world (Reid *et al.*, 2002; Velusamy *et al.*, 2010).

(i)Multidisciplinary approach strategy: This is a very crucial aspect of the integrated approach to food safety. It involves the incorporation of all those who have one thing or the other to do with food safety from ‘farm to fork’ and ‘stable to table’ to play their appropriate roles to ensure the safety of food for human consumption. These people include medical doctors, veterinary doctors, nurses, paramedics and technical personnel. Also the role of non professionals such as the farmers and fishermen must not be down-played because they are crucial to the food reaching the final consumers in good and wholesome condition (Newell *et al.*, 2010). This multidisciplinary approach ensures a one health concept for food safety in which all relevant professions collaborate to ensure a healthy world.

Other measures involved in the integrated approach to food safety include the improved monitoring of foodborne infections and risk assessment at all levels, transparency in the work of the supervisory authorities and improving food hygiene in commercial catering and the home.

In order to have a truly integrated approach to food safety the following points should always be born in mind:

- ❖ Food safety strategies should be risk-based and cover the entire food chain.
- ❖ The follow-up and reporting of foodborne disease outbreaks should be improved.
- ❖ An integrated, multidisciplinary approach to food safety, that addresses problems at the source, should be adopted.
- ❖ In-house control systems based on the HACCP approach are needed.
- ❖ Food inspection and monitoring results should be made public.
- ❖ Training of catering personnel and the education of consumers in food hygiene should be improved.
- ❖ Communication and collaboration between food safety and environmental protection officials should be improved.
- ❖ Adequate resources should be assigned for the detection of emerging risks (Buncic, 2006).

Threats and hazards linked to food safety

Numerous threats and hazards are associated with food safety. These threats emanate right from the preharvest to the post harvest phase from “farm to fork” and from “stable to table”. Threats and hazards to food safety are contaminations of food along the food chain which are capable of affecting human health. These contaminations are due to pathogenic microorganisms, poisonous substances, chemicals and other substances that have deleterious effects on human health (Marler, 2011; Newell *et al.*, 2010).

More than 200 different food borne diseases have been described. Most of these diseases are infections, caused by a variety of bacteria, viruses, and parasites that can be food borne. Other diseases are poisonings, caused by harmful toxins or chemicals that have contaminated the food, for example, poisonous mushrooms (Newell *et al.*, 2010; Mukhopadhyay and Ramaswamy, 2011). These different diseases have many different symptoms and manifestations, so there is no one "syndrome" that is food borne illness. However, the microbe or toxin enters the body through the gastrointestinal tract, and often causes the first symptoms there, such as nausea, vomiting, abdominal cramps, and diarrhea is common symptoms in many food borne diseases. Many microbes can spread in more than one way, so it is difficult to always know whether a disease is food borne or not. The distinction

matters, because public health authorities need to know how a particular disease is spreading in order to take the appropriate steps to stop it. For example, *Escherichia coli* O157:H7 (*E.coli* O157:H7) infections can spread through contaminated food, contaminated drinking water, contaminated swimming water, and from toddler to toddler at a day care center. Depending on which means of spread caused a case, the measures to stop other cases from occurring could range from removing contaminated food from stores, chlorinating a swimming pool, or closing a child day care center (Duffy *et al.*, 2008).

A variety of good agricultural and manufacturing practices can reduce the spread of Microbes among animals and prevent the contamination of foods. Careful review of the whole food production process can identify the principal hazards and the control points where contamination can be prevented, limited, or eliminated. A formal method for evaluating the control of risk in foods exists; it is called the Hazard Analysis Critical Control Point, or HACCP System. This was first developed by NASA to make sure that the food eaten by astronauts was safe but now has wide applications worldwide. HACCP safety principles are now being applied to an increasing spectrum of foods, including meat, poultry, and seafood.

The most commonly recognized food borne infections are those caused by the bacteria *Campylobacter*, *Salmonella*, and *E.coli* O157:H7, and by a group of viruses called *calicivirus*, also known as the *Norwalk* and *Norwalk-like* viruses. But many other pathogens are implicated in food borne infections in different parts of the world. Some more common in certain places than others places depending on the optimum conditions for the organism and food habits of people in various geographical locations of the world.

Campylobacter: is a bacterial pathogen that causes fever, diarrhea, and abdominal cramps. It is the most commonly identified bacterial cause of diarrheal illness in the world. These bacteria live in the intestines of healthy birds, and most raw poultry meat has *Campylobacter* on it. Eating chicken that is not well cooked, or other food that has been contaminated with juices dripping from raw chicken, is the commonest source of this infection (Mank and Davies, 2008).

Salmonella: is also a bacterium that is widespread in the intestines of birds, reptiles and mammals. It can spread to humans via a variety of different foods of animal origin. The illness it causes, salmonellosis, typically includes fever, diarrhea and abdominal cramps. In persons with poor underlying health or weakened immune systems, it can invade the bloodstream and cause life-threatening infections (Mukhopadhyay and Ramaswamy, 2011).

E.coli O157:H7: is a bacterial pathogen that has a reservoir in cattle and other similar animals. Human illness typically follows consumption of food or water that has been contaminated with microscopic amounts of cow feces. The sickness it causes manifests as severe and bloody diarrhea and painful abdominal cramps, without much fever. In 3% to 5% of cases, a complication called hemolytic uremic syndrome (HUS) may occur many weeks after the first onset of symptoms. This severe complication includes temporary anemia, profuse bleeding, and kidney failure (McMeekin *et al.*, 2010).

Shigellosis: caused by *Shigella* species especially *shigella dysenteriae* is an infection of the gastrointestinal tract of humans and higher primates that can be very life threatening if diarrhea and vomiting are not adequately controlled which are the common presentations of the disease. Good hygiene and thorough cooking of food is essential to control this pathogen (Kohler *et al.*, 2008).

Vibrio Cholera: this pathogen is similar to *Shigella species*. Death can occur in dehydrated individuals in a matter of hours. Strict hygienic measures are important in the control such as boiling water before drinking, proper disposal of sewage, avoiding raw sea foods and excluding infected individuals from handling food or food related items. Other species of vibrio are also important including *vibrio parahaemolyticus* and *vibrio vulnificus* (Newell, *et al.*, 2010).

Yersinia enterocolitica: cause yersiniosis mainly via consumption of unpasteurized milk, milk products, water and pork. Prolonged cooking of meat can eliminate the organism and pasteurization of milk (Gálvez *et al.*, 2010).

Listeriosis: caused by *listeria monocytogenes*, it is an invasive infection of humans and livestock and sometimes it occurs in the non-invasive form. Humans acquire this infection by consuming raw milk, cheese, ready-to-eat meat products, poultry products, sea food products, vegetables and fresh salads. Hygiene is crucial in the control and immunocompromised individuals should avoid high risk food (Newell *et al.*, 2010).

Staphylococcus aureus infection: This ubiquitous gram positive bacterial pathogen produces a wide range of enterotoxins in food and causes the food borne intoxication staphylo-enterotoxigenesis. Measures to control it in addition to hygiene includes chilling of cooked food in small quantities rapidly, store cooked food or heat treated food at <4°C, avoid delays between cooking and eating of food and minimize number of people handling food (White *et al.*, 2002).

Clostridium poisoning: caused by the ubiquitous bacteria *clostridium perfringens* which produces the enterotoxin type A and also B, C, D, E, F, and G. Type A is the one that causes food borne disease (Labbe, 2000).

Some other bacterial organisms that can cause hazards associated with food include *Bacillus cereus* and *Clostridium botulinum* especially in young children.

Some viral pathogens important in food safety include:

Calicivirus or *Norwalk-like virus*: is an extremely common cause of food borne illness, though it is rarely diagnosed because the laboratory test is not widely available. It causes an acute gastrointestinal illness, usually with more vomiting than diarrhea that resolves within two days. Unlike many food borne pathogens that have animal reservoirs, it is believed that Norwalk-like viruses spread primarily from one infected person to another. Infected kitchen workers can contaminate a salad or sandwich as they prepare it, if they have the virus on their hands. Infected fishermen can contaminate oysters as they harvest them.

Rotavirus: This virus is a common cause of gastroenteritis in children less than 2 years of age. It is transmitted through the faecal-oral route. It is self-limiting except in severely dehydrated individuals.

Some common diseases are occasionally food borne, even though they are usually transmitted by other routes. These include infections caused by hepatitis A, and the parasites *Giardia lamblia* and *Cryptosporidium*. *Cryptosporidium* for example is commonly transmitted through the faecal-oral route and via water contaminated with oocysts of the organism. There was a major outbreak of cryptosporidiosis in Milwaukee, USA in 1993 involved more than 400,000 people that it attracted world attention to the organism (Mackenzie *et al.*, 1994). Even streptococcus has been transmitted occasionally through food. In addition to disease caused by direct infection, some food borne diseases are caused by the presence of a toxin in the food that was produced by a microbe in the food. For example, the bacterium *Staphylococcus aureus* can grow in some foods and produce a toxin that causes intense vomiting. The rare but deadly disease botulism occurs when the bacterium *Clostridium botulinum* grows and produces a powerful paralytic toxin in foods. These toxins can produce illness even if the microbes that produced them are no longer there. Other toxins and poisonous chemicals can cause food borne illness. People can become ill if a pesticide is inadvertently added to a food, or if naturally poisonous substances are used to prepare a meal. Every year, people become ill after mistaking poisonous mushrooms for safe species, or after eating poisonous reef fishes. Various zoonotic diseases are a major source of danger in the handling and processing of food hence meat inspectors and authorities concerned should be on the lookout for such in order to minimize risk posed to man.

Chemical hazards in food include the following:

- (a) Lead poisoning
- (b) Arsenic
- (c) Cadmium
- (d) Mercury
- (e) Polychlorinated Biphenyls(PCBs)
- (f) Polychlorinated Naphthalenes(PCNs)
- (g) Dioxins
- (h) Insecticides e.g. Chlorinated Hydrocarbons and Organophosphates
- (i) Herbicides

- (j) Fungicides
 - (k) Rodenticides
 - (l) Fertilizers
 - (m) Some Growth Promoters including the synthetic hormone Diethylstilbestrol(DES) which was associated with causing early puberty in girls exposed to it via pork over a long period of time
 - (n) Antimicrobials: antimicrobial residues in food are not acceptable not only because of their harmful side effects in man over a period of time but also because they could induce development of resistance to such drugs by the microorganisms in question.
 - (o) Anthelmintics: Residues of these drugs have been known to cause teratogenic effects.
 - (p) Tranquilizers
 - (q) Mycotoxins
 - (r) Algal toxins
 - (s) Plant toxins
 - (t) Food additives: such as nitrites, polyphosphates, antioxidants, e.t.c.
 - (u) Plastic Packaging Materials
- (Buncic, 2002)

Some genetically modified food have been considered not the best for human consumption and the controversy still rages on about the suitability or otherwise of genetically modified food for human consumption but recent developments are tending to change people's attitude towards genetically modified food on a positive note especially with the recent outbreaks of *E. coli* infections in Europe with Germany hardest hit which is believed to have originated from an organic farm (Marler, 2011).

Recent concerns related to food safety

There has been a lot of concern regarding the safety of food for human consumption. The recent trends seen in global food production, processing, distribution and preparation are creating an increasing demand for food safety research in order to ensure a safer global food supply. The WHO organization is concerned about current trends regarding food borne infections which is estimated to kill about 2.2 million people annually in less developed countries, about 1.9million of whom are children and women dying of food borne and water borne diarrheal illnesses worldwide (WHO, 2011). As this paper is being written the world is experiencing the worse outbreak of *E.coli* infection in recent history which has claimed many lives with thousands hospitalized (Marler, 2011). The outbreak has affected more women than men and mostly middle aged individuals unlike many food pathogens that affect mainly children (Perrett, 2011). The food mostly involved are bean sprouts, cucumbers, lettuce and tomatoes and the origin of the new mutant strain *E. coli* 0104:H4 responsible for the infection remains a mystery but research is ongoing and perhaps in some time to come the origin could be traced successfully (Allecia, 2011; Recknagel, 2011). The *E. coli* epidemic is said to have peaked already and is on the decline (Recknagel, 2011). In the light of this great concerns continue to be expressed about the safety of food worldwide.

The increase in public concern regarding food hazards and decline in public trust in food risk regulators suggests that there is a need to identify the actual concerns held by the public regarding specific food hazards in order to develop effective risk communication.

CONCLUSION

The current world population stands at about 7 billion people on earth (Rosenberg, 2011). To safe guard the human species on this planet and ensure healthy continuity from generation to generation in a fast changing world there is a need for a more all-encompassing and more efficient integrated approach to food safety.

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